

Experimental Investigations on the Partial Connection Theory in Composite Beams at Elevated Temperatures

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ABSTRACT

Composite beams integrating a steel section, profiled sheet and concrete chord are widely used in composite construction. In the structural design, the theory of partial shear connections provided in EN 1994-1-1 (1) offers the possibility of optimising the use of shear connectors and thus improve the economic efficiency of the structure. However, the EN 1994-1-2 (2) requires consideration of the temperature dependent variation of the longitudinal shear forces when applying the partial shear connection in the fire resistance design. Unfortunately, there is no further information in the Eurocodes on how to account for this change in longitudinal shear force, which severely limits the application of partial composite theory. Research at TUM has investigated the feasibility of partial shear connection theory for composite beams with solid slab under elevated temperature, resulting in proposing a novel methodology that facilitates its application under specific conditions (3). This paper describes further research aimed at adapting this methodology to composite beams with profiled sheets. To investigate this, a fire test was carried out on two 9 m long composite beams with profiled decking. During this test, temperature and deformations were measured to compare with the analytical approaches for calculating the bending capacity according to EN 1994-1-2 (2).

Keywords: Composite beam, Fire test, Elevated temperature, Shear connection

1 INTRODUCTION

The composite construction method is characterised by the best possible utilisation of the respective material properties of the composite partners concrete and steel and is a widely used and economical construction method in building and bridge construction. To speed up the construction process, profiled sheeting can be used, allowing work to be carried out without the need for additional slab formwork. Different structural requirements and optimisation of concrete consumption can be met by adapting the size and geometry of the profiled panels. In order to provide the composite action of the cross section, the arrangement of shear connectors is essential. The most commonly used are headed shear studs, which are characterised by high availability and an economic welding process. The degree of shear connection is mainly influenced by number and arrangement of the connecting elements. The provided degree of shear connection is characterized by the ratio η/η_f and thus indicates the percentage of the longitudinal concrete chord shear force N_{cf} belonging to the fully plastic moment $M_{pl,rd}$ that is transferred by the shear connectors. For economic reasons, it makes sense to provide a full shear connection only if this is necessary for the verification requirements and to reduce the number of headed shear studs wherever possible. For single-span beams, in areas of positive bending moment, EN 1994-1-1 (1) permits a reduction in the degree of shear connection to a minimum of 40 %. Where there is a partial shear connection, there is a relative displacement, known as slip, at the interface between the steel flange and the concrete chord. This leads to the requirement in (1) for a ductility of shear connectors of more than 6 mm

(Fig. 1). The minimum degree of shear connection is intended to limit the occurring slip and prevent a zipper-like failure of the shear connection. Experimental results from (4) indicate that even lower degrees of shear connections are sufficient to avoid a brittle failure.

Fig. 1. Composite action with a) full shear connection; and b) partial shear connection

For a structural fire design of composite structures, the application of partial interaction theory according to the current state of standardization (2) is not straightforward. In (2) only the following note is provided: „In case of design by partial shear connection in the fire situation, the variation of longitudinal shear forces in function of the heating should be considered.” How this requirement can be practically implemented for the fire design of structures is not elaborated. The use of advanced calculation models acc. to section 4.4 in (2) are generally not feasible in small and medium-sized engineering offices. Therefore, it is desirable to define simple boundary conditions for the design of composite beams in partial shear connection for the fire safe design. For composite beams with a solid concrete slab, the application of partial interaction theory in fire cases is initially discussed in (5) and elaborated in detail in (6) (3). In (3), three effects are identified that are present in the shear connection of a simply supported beam exposed to elevated temperatures:

- Effect 1: Negative slip due to thermal elongation of the steel section
- Effect 2: Positive slip due to the high thermal gradient in the composite beam resulting in bending (thermal curvature)
- Effect 3: Positive slip due to mechanical load resulting in bending

The results in (3) particularly indicate that due to opposing effects in the development of slip during a fire event, only a relatively low ductility of the connectors is required, provided that the minimum degree of shear connection according to DIN EN 1994-1-1 (1) is maintained. This finding can possibly also be transferred to composite beams with profiled decking, which generally guarantee at ambient temperature an even higher ductility of the shear connection than composite beams with solid slabs. To validate the load-bearing behaviour of composite beams with profiled decking, a fire test on two composite beams was conducted as part of the research project Aif 21403 N. The conducted experiments, and results of which are discussed in excerpts below.

2 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

2.1 Testing program

Two composite beams with a HEB 300 steel profile of grade S355J2 and a span of 9 meters were examined. For comparison of the test results, the dimensions and support conditions were consistent with those of the beams from a previous research project presented in (6). Two different types of trapezoidal deck sheets were used for the beams. The span of the trapezoidal sheets was perpendicular to the steel profile axis. Due to their widespread use and available test data under ambient temperature (7) (8), the Cofraplus60 sheets from ArcelorMittal and Comfloor80 from Tata

Steel were selected. Both types of decking fall within the scope of DIN EN 1994-1-1 (1). While the Comflor80 sheet has a profile sheet height of 80 mm and an average rib width of 135 mm, the Cofraplus60 sheet, with a profile sheet height of 58 mm, is less high but significantly slimmer due to an average rib width of 81.5 mm (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Geometry of the tested deck sheets Cofraplus60 and Comflor80

As the focus of the experiments was primarily on the potential application of the partial connection theory for the fire design, a relatively low degree of shear connection was chosen for both beams, that was even below the requirements of (1) for use in the ultimate limit state (ULS) design. Headed studs with a diameter of 19 mm and a height of 125 mm were arranged equidistantly along the length of the beams. The welding of the headed studs was performed through the pre-punched trapezoidal sheets directly onto the flange of the steel profile. The width of the concrete slab was set at 1000 mm and the height at 150 mm for the beam with Cofraplus60, and at 187 mm for the beam with Comflor80 (Fig. 3). Both beams were reinforced with two layers of Q355 reinforcement mesh of grade B500B. The dimensions of the two beams are shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Cross section and dimensions of the tested composite Beams; with a) Comflor80 an b) Cofraplus60 decking

2.2 Material properties

A concrete grade of C35/45 was used for the manufacture of the composite beams. For the testing of compressive strength, modulus of elasticity, and splitting tensile strength, a total of 18 concrete cylinders and 6 concrete cubes were produced and tested according to Figure 4. The material tests were conducted on the day of the fire test, after 155 days of air storage of the specimens. The tests gave $f_{c,cube} = 54.1 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $f_{c,cyl} = 49.97 \text{ N/mm}^2$ and $f_{ct} = 3.63 \text{ N/mm}^2$. The material tensile strength for the headed stud was 521 N/mm^2 and for the HEB 300 S355 the yield strength was $f_y = 414 \text{ N/mm}^2$, they were taken from the manufacturer's material certificates.

Fig. 4. Different conducted material tests on concrete specimen

2.3 Instrumentation

To capture the horizontal and vertical deformations during the test, cable transducers were installed outside the furnace. These were used to measure the deflection at mid-span as well as the relative displacement between the concrete slab and the upper flange of the steel beam (Fig 5). Additionally, more transducers were installed at the ends of the beams to record the absolute change in length of the steel profile. The furnace temperature was measured using 20 plate thermocouples, which were evenly distributed beneath the steel profiles inside the furnace. The temperature on the surface and inside the specimens (Fig 5) was recorded using Type K thermocouples with fibreglass insulation. For measurements on the steel profile, the thermocouples were welded onto the surface of the profile. Measurements were taken over the entire cross-sections as shown in Figure 3, for both flanges of the steel profile and its web. The placement of the thermocouples on the steel profile was staggered along the length of the beam around its longitudinal axis to capture potential temperature differences due to shading effects. For measurements in the concrete, Type K thermocouples were chained together at 30 mm distance. These were placed in the concrete chord prior to casting (Fig. 5) and staggered along the length of the beam. Measurements were taken from the bottom edge of the trapezoidal sheet upwards. Since the temperature development of the headed studs played a crucial role in the research project, some of the studs were provided with a 3 mm diameter and 100 mm deep borehole along their central longitudinal axis. By inserting a pearl Type K thermocouple, the temperature of the stud could be measured 25 mm above the flange.

Fig. 5. Measuring concept for fire tests; a) deformations; b) Temperatures on c) Steel section and d) in the concrete

2.4 Testing procedure

The experiments were conducted in the ceiling test furnace at the iBMB of TU Braunschweig. The furnace chamber measures 8.0 m x 4.0 m. The ends of the beams penetrate the furnace wall and are supported on either side by hinges outside the furnace. Porous concrete elements were laid on top of the concrete beams to seal the furnace. The load was applied to each beam using three force-controlled hydraulic cylinders.

To prevent damage to the furnace resulting in uncontrolled heat release, lime-sanded bricks were used to limit maximum deformation to 350 mm ($\sim L/25$). Figure 6 illustrates the setup.

Fig. 6. Test Setup for the fire test

The tests shown in Fig. 7 were performed in accordance with EN 1365-3 (9). To minimise the effects of short-term relaxation, the test was started with a load of 90 kN per hydraulic cylinder and held for 20 minutes. After this period, the furnace was heated according to the ISO 834 standard fire (10). Temperature control was achieved using plate thermocouples in the furnace chamber, adhering to the specified temperature progression from EN 1363-1 (11). As deformation limit of the two composite beams occurred at different times, the beam exhibiting the first signs of significant non-linear deformations was disconnected from the hydraulic circuit. Once the second beam also reached the deformation limit of $L/25$, it was likewise disconnected from the hydraulic circuit. Subsequently, the presses were retracted. The heating was maintained for a minimum duration of 30 minutes to monitor the further temperature development. After the fire exposure ended, measurements of the component temperatures continued for an additional 15 minutes to capture the onset of the cooling process.

Fig. 7. Fotos of test Setup before the start of the experiment

3 TEST RESULTS

3.1 Observations

Under pure mechanical loading, both beams exhibited the behaviour expected due to their differing stiffnesses. Due to the higher flexural rigidity of the beam with the Comflor80 decking, resulting from its higher degree of shear connection and the thicker concrete slab, this beam displayed lesser deflection and slip compared to the beam with Cofraplus60. After about 15 minutes of fire exposure, moist spots appeared on the concrete surface (Figure 8, left), a phenomenon attributable to mass transport of water vapor that condensed on the surface (12) (13). During the test, spalling of

the concrete slab occurred, announced by loud popping sounds (see Figure 8, mid). Slip due to the mechanical loading was observed at the ends of the beams, which reversed direction shortly after the onset of fire exposure. After 21.5 minutes of fire exposure, the beam with Comflor80 experienced a nonlinear increase in deformations, necessitating the disconnection of the hydraulic circuit at a deflection of 320 mm. The beam with Cofraplus60 reached the deflection limit after 24 minutes. After the beams cooled, shear failure of the concrete ribs was observed. (Fig. 8, right).

Fig. 8. Observations during and after the fire test

3.2 Temperature Measurements

During the test, the temperature measured at the installed thermocouples was recorded every 15 seconds (Figure 9). The temperature in the furnace showed good agreement with the ISO standard fire curve and remained within the tolerances as depicted in (11). However, it was noted that the average temperature in the furnace beneath the beam with the Comflor80 decking was about 23 °C higher than beneath the beam with the Cofraplus60 decking. This temperature difference can be attributable to shading effects and the arrangement of the burners in the furnace.

Fig. 9. Average recorded furnace temperature during the experiment

As shown in Figure 10, generally higher temperatures were measured on the steel profile of the composite beam with the Comflor80 decking compared to the beam with the Cofraplus60 decking. As expected, the top flange of the steel section, partially protected by the concrete slab, heated more slowly than the web and bottom flange. The temperatures recorded in the headed studs, 25mm above the beam flange, reached approximately 200°C at the time the beams reached the deformation limit. Although the reference point for the temperature induced reduction in resistance of headed studs in (2), following (5), is 5 mm above the beam flange, implying higher temperatures, it is assumed that no significant reduction in resistance has occurred within the test period.

Fig. 10. Average temperature on steel profile during the experiment; left side for the Comflor80 beam; right side for Cofraplus60 beam. The average value was calculated from the measurement points shown on the right.

3.3 Mechanical response

The deflection of the beams was measured at mid-span and is given for the beam with Cofraplus60 decking in Figure 11. In the first 20 minutes, the beams were subjected to purely mechanical loading. Due to this load, the composite beam with Cofraplus60 experienced a deflection of approximately 40 mm. With the onset of the ISO- standard fire (Fig. 11, b), there was a significant increase in deformations. After about 24 minutes of fire exposure, the presses for the beam with Cofraplus60 were disconnected from the hydraulic circuit (Fig. 11, c) following a significant non-linear increase in deformations and upon reaching the deformation limit of 350 mm.

Fig. 11. Measured vertical displacement on Cofraplus60 beam at mid-span over the total test time

As previously explained, partial shear connection results in a relative displacement between the steel beam and the concrete slab. This load-bearing behaviour requires that the connectors used are ductile. Recent research projects (14) (8) (7), which involved push-out-test tests with the two present trapezoidal profiled sheets, demonstrated a very high deformation capacity of $\Delta\delta \gg 6$ mm of the headed studs at room temperature. The three effects of slip development described in [6] can be identified in the measurements from the tests. Analysing the slip measurements in Figure 12, a positive slip developed due to the mechanical load in the initial state of the experiment. As the heating from the fire load progressed, the thermal expansion of the steel profile became apparent, and the slip became negative. Just before the composite beam was unloaded, there was a significant increase in deflection at mid-span, resulting in a reversal of the slip trend. When the presses were disconnected (Fig. 12, c), the beam was unloaded and experienced no further deflection, and it rebounded by the amount of elastic deformation. However, as the furnace temperature continued to rise until the fire exposure was terminated after 30 minutes, further significant negative slip development occurred. Only after the end of the experiment and the onset of the cooling phase (Fig. 12, d) the slip trend reverse due to the contraction of the steel beam.

a) Mechanical load applied b) Start ISO- standard fire c) Mechanical load relief d) End ISO- standard fire

Fig. 12. Measured slip on the beams end for the total experimental time

4 COMPARISON BETWEEN EXPERIMENTAL LOAD CAPACITY AND ANALYTICAL VALUES

The moment resistances for composite beams with partial shear connection can be determined using a fully plastic method according to EN 1994-1-1 (1). This method is extended to fire design in the informative Annex E of EN 1994-1-2 (2), illustrating the scenario where the plastic neutral axis is within the concrete slab (Fig. 13). For other locations of the neutral axis, it is stated, "A similar approach may be used when the neutral axis is not in the concrete slab but in the steel beam." (2). This implies that the fully plastic calculation method can also be applied for different positions of the neutral axis. Due to the rapid heating of the steel profile compared to the concrete slab during a fire, the position of the neutral axis shifts upwards over the duration of the fire. As explained in

Capture 1, the applications of the given formulations are limited by the condition that the variation of longitudinal shear forces at elevated temperatures should be considered (2). However, the $M_{Rd,fi}$ for 20 °C and the time at which the deformation limit is reached, considered as the failure criterion, is calculated as follows. The calculation utilizes the temperatures of individual cross-sectional components as an average value over the entire beam length. The fully plastic moment resistances was determined by using the given material parameters and an experimentally determined headed stud load-capacity $P_{Rd,fi,20^\circ C}$ of 57.5 kN taken from (8). The plastic moment resistances $M_{Rd,fi}$ are calculated to be 926 kNm at 20 °C and 421 kNm after 24 minutes fire exposure. The acting bending moment M_{Ed} caused by the hydraulic jacks, superimposed with the dead weight of the composite beam, can be estimated at approximately 430 kNm. For the beam with the Cofraplus60 there is good agreement with the analytical method according to (2). The interaction between bending moment and vertical shear force was neglected for the determination of $M_{Rd,fi}$. It was also assumed that the relatively low temperatures in the concrete chord compression zone and in the headed stud do not require a reduction in their material resistances.

Fig. 13. Calculation of the sagging moment resistance taken from (2) Annex E

5 SUMMARY

This article described a fire test conducted on two composite beams with open shaped profiled deck sheets. Throughout the duration of the experiment, the temperature development, the slip and the deflection at mid-span were recorded. Under purely mechanical loading, both beams exhibited vertical deformation consistent with their calculated stiffness. With the onset of the fire and rising temperatures, a continuous increase in vertical deformations was observed. After 24 minutes of fire exposure, the beam with Cofraplus60 reached the defined failure criterion of a vertical deformation at mid-span. The composite beam presented showed good agreement with the moment resistance determined according to (2). These capacities were calculated using a fully plastic determination of moment capacity according to (1), applying temperature-dependent reduction factors from (2). A slip pattern was measured which changed direction during the test as described in (3). Since the absolute value of the slip measured immediately after unloading was 8 mm, this was well below the deformation capacity of the headed studs in the profiled sheets used. It can therefore be concluded that there was no classical failure of the shear connection due to exceeding the deformation capacity of the connectors during the experiment. The experiments presented form the basis for the development and validation of numerical models to further investigate the structural behaviour of composite beams under fire exposure.

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